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FEATURES OF INFORMATION SUPPORT OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

Information support of enterprises that are subjects of international business has its specifics since it is already information management in the global context, where it is important to take into account cultural, technological, and regulatory differences between countries.

Considering scientific sources, the following characteristics of information support of international business enterprises can be identified (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Modern manifestations of information support of international business enterprises (compiled based on [1], [2])

The first factor that determines the specificity of information support is the factor of globality and branching. In international business, enterprises carry out sufficiently extensive activities (spatial expansion of divisions, customers, suppliers, partners). In such conditions, information support must

comply with the principle of security, effective communication, and data exchange between all parties, taking into account the cultural and legal conditions of different countries. The next factor is cyber security. Today reality produces a new threat, which is precisely related to the technical manifestation of information security. Due to the growth of international business operations, the risk of cyber-attacks and data security breaches is also increasing. Therefore, the information support of international business enterprises should include effective cyber security strategies that can protect the confidential and personal information of customers from unauthorized access and cyber criminals.

Another feature is cross-cultural communication and localization. International business enterprises must adapt their information systems and communication approaches to different cultural contexts. This means ensuring the localization of information support, namely information resources (websites, software, documentation, specifics of the organization of work with information, considering the norms and values of the host countries). The next factor that characterizes the specifics of modern information support is legislative regulation. In the course of their activities, international business enterprises encounter national legal norms and regulatory mechanisms that operate in different countries and are often different. Therefore, information support must follow these requirements, most often this means compliance with legal norms regarding data processing and confidentiality.

Use of analytics and data. According to this component, the information support of international business enterprises should include effective data analysis tools that will allow obtaining valuable data from various sources. The specificity of information support as a technological component is taking into account the continuous development of the modern technological environment, therefore it is important to constantly improve own information support, which must be flexible and ready for the introduction of new technologies, such as virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence, blockchain, etc., which can improve the efficiency and security of business processes of international business enterprises.

References

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2. Didenko M.V. Information support for management of foreign economic activity based on innovative technologies. *Economic Bulletin of the University*. 2021. No. 37. P. 128–132.